

LINGUISTICS: MODERN DIRECTIONS AND ANALYSIS AND PROBLEMS

Nasrullayev Odil Kutbitdinovich

Tashkent State University of Applied Sciences

Senior teacher of the Department of Foreign Language and Literature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7857631>

Abstract: In this article illustrated the article focused on the modern directions of linguistics, reflecting on its current relevance.

Keywords: linguistics-linguistics, terminology, sociolinguistics, static linguistics, computer linguistics

Introduction.

The term linguistics is actively used in a number of European countries: English, French, German, Spanish, Russian and other languages, referring to the science of the language. The root of this word is lingua, which means language. Consequently, the alternative to the term linguistics in Uzbek is figurative linguistics, which enters into a synonymous relationship.

The science of linguistics or linguistics studies and analyzes the weapon of communication – language as a system – as a whole object, which is a kind of complex social phenomenon. In the same process, it is observed in different manifestations, forms. It comes from the essence of a language with a social character, from the fact that it must be studied, examined from different sides, and that this is absolutely correct in terms of the point of science.

Linguistics is an extremely powerful sign of spirituality, manifested in the following manifestations in the process of learning a language with a wealth of nationality:

- ❖ Dynamic linguistics;
- ❖ Static linguistics;
- ❖ Sinxron linguistics;
- ❖ Diaxron linguistics;
- ❖ Intralinguistic;
- ❖ Extralinguistic;
- ❖ Paralinguistic;
- ❖ Psixolinguistic;
- ❖ Sotsiolinguistic;
- ❖ Mathematical linguistics;
- ❖ Kompyuter linguistics;
- ❖ Cognitive linguistics;
- ❖ Pragmalinguistic;
- ❖ The linguaculturalogiya.

Discussion.

Dynamic linguistics. Dynamic linguistics mainly studies language in its real existence, in the active performance of various tasks in the communicative process, in "progress", in change.

Static linguistics. Static linguistics separates and describes a particular period (slice) in language activity that is fully synchronized. This area of linguistics, unlike dynamic linguistics,

completely deviates from the process of development and change in the language, without approaching it, examines the state of a certain "hardened" part of the language associated with the current – modern period.

Synchronous linguistics. Synchronous linguistics is inextricably linked with static and structural linguistics, serving to describe the "hardened", "stationary" state of a language in a given period.

Diachronic linguistics. Diachronic linguistics is inextricably linked with dynamic and atomistic linguistics, studying the laws and results of the development of language and language units.

Intralinguistics (internal linguistics). Internal linguistics studies the system connection, relationship of language units, without dependence on extralinguistic factors. The research source of internal linguistics is phonology, lexicology and grammar.

Extralinguistics (external linguistics). External linguistics studies the development and function of language in relation to such factors as socio-political, socio-historical, ethnic, geographical. Accordingly, this linguistics examines language as a social phenomenon.

Paralinguistics. Paralinguistics is directly related to speech activity and is an area that studies a number of aspects such as hand and face movements (gesture, facial expressions), height of speech, expressive-emotional paint, which occur simultaneously with the expression of thought in the process of speech.

Psycholinguistics. Psycholinguistics as a generalization (synthesis) of psychology and Linguistics studies the process of speech from the point of view of the point of content, in terms of communicative significance, orientation of the act of speech to a specific socio-practical purpose, compliance with it. He pays special attention to the unity of form and content in speech – in the expression of thought.

Psycholinguistics places particular emphasis on the generation and reception of speech units based on linguistic possibilities, mental states in the speech process (thought switching-expression and perception), in which the conditions (situational), similarity (analogy), differentiation (differentiation), affectivity, the issues of the mental state of the speaker and the listener.

Sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistics is formed from the necessary and logical connection of sociology and Linguistics and deals with the question of the relationship of society and language (language and society). He interprets language as a social phenomenon. In this respect, the most important, fundamental problem of sociolinguistics is the examination of language - the nature of language as a social phenomenon, determining its place and significance in society, in linguistics.

Sociolinguistics mainly studies the connection between language and social relations, social life, phenomena of progress, facts, the reasons for this connection. On the other hand, this field analyzes the phenomena, processes, changes that are formed as a result of the influence of social life in the language, that is, external-extralinguistic factors (factors), in the survival and development of society. So sociolinguistics studies how social factors affect language, how they manifest themselves in the language system (structure), in what form they are reflected.

Let us remind you that sociolinguistics expands its activities with statistical data, population lists and survey data methodology¹.

Mathematical linguistics. Mathematical linguistics examines the possibilities of application of mathematical methods (such as the statistical method, information theory, etc.) in the process of learning and describing a language.

Computer linguistics. Computer linguistics is a branch of Applied Linguistics, the main purpose of which is to solve problems related to linguistics in a computer medium, directly under its "leadership". More precisely, computer linguistics is actively serving in a number of processes, such as teaching languages (learning), evaluating knowledge of a particular discipline, editing texts, translating from one language to another, conducting statistical research.

Cognitive linguistics. Cognitive linguistics is one of the newest areas in linguistics. This linguistics arose from the necessary interconnection of cognitology (a science that studies human knowledge) and Linguistics, with the aim of working cooperatively.

Pragmalinguistics. Pragmatic linguistics is the result of educational (empirik) Studies, Research at a new stage, formed on the basis of the achievements, results of structural linguistics. It takes as a system the situation of application of the linguistic unit, its speech activity. Accordingly, it studies, examines a certain unity in speech activity, in reality, in speech manifestation, in cooperation with various nonlinear factors and various levels, in their interaction with them.

Linguoculturalogy. Linguoculturalogy was formed on the basis of the fields of linguistics, cultural studies, ethnography, Psycholinguistics. He studies the interaction and influence of culture, Ethnos, national mentalism on the principles of the anthropocentric paradigm.

Result.

As a generality, as noted, the science of linguistics studies the language system through its various identities, fields, with its whole essence, complexity, communicative infinite possibilities. In the same process, he works in interaction, cooperation with a number of disciplines, actively participates in the coverage of such urgent and extremely complex issues as language and society, language and history, language and development, language and thinking, language and speech.

Conclusion.

The science of linguistics serves to confirm and prove that one of the most important, most basic, unmatched criteria for the development, prosperity of society is the language-the weapon of communication. It also serves as a solid foundation in the development of creative thinking in it, the uniqueness of the construction of thinking and mother tongue in the native language, its radical difference from other languages, the absorption of the reflection of the universe "on its own", the formation of a national consciousness, a national worldview, national pride and ideology.

¹ В.А.Аврорин. Проблемы изучения функциональной стороны языка (к вопросу о предмете социоллингвистики). Л., 1975, 242-245- бетлар.

References:

1. Role-playing games in teaching foreign languages // INR No. 4, 1989.
2. Work on a project on teaching English // INR Methodology for teaching foreign languages // INR No. 2, 3, 2000.
3. Saidahmedov N. New pedagogical technologies. "Enlightenment" 2003.
4. Alimov Sh.S. Course of lectures on modern teaching technologies. Andijan, 2009.
5. Douglas Brown. Teaching by principles. Pearson Longman, USA. 1996.
6. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.